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THE EUROPEAN UNION AND THE FUTURE OF THE UNITED STATES AS A MAJOR SUPER POWER IN GLOBAL POLITICS

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ABSTRACT

This paper explored the post Cold War cooperation between the United States and the European Union with an effort to discover the implication of such cooperation for the status of the US as a major superpower in present day international politics. A subtle competition from the EU end of the relationship is discernible. Using a qualitative approach, the paper examined trade data released by the United States Census Bureau and the U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis and also data provided by Eurostat and discovered that US imports exceeds its exports while the EU exports exceeds its imports. This accounts for the higher share of world trade by the EU vis-à-vis the US. Therefore, contrary to the realist prediction of the decline and final demise of Europe's global influence, the EU's global influence is actually on the rise. It is the conclusion of the study that if this trend continues, the EU will eventually surpass the US in strength and thereby put the EU at preponderance above the US in the future. It is recommended that the US should address the imbalance if it would maintain its preeminent position in global politics in the future.

KEYWORDS

The United States of America, The European Union, Major Superpower, Global Politics, Preponderance.

INTRODUCTION

From the 1920s through the early 1940s, the United States has been aloof in its relations with Europe and other parts of the world. This is evidenced in its refusal to join the League of Nations, even though Woodrow Wilson, the then American President pioneered the formation of the organization. At the outbreak of World War II, the United States did not change its position until 1945 when it joined the Allied forces and the consequent dropping of the hydrogen bomb on the Japanese cities of Hiroshima and Nagasaki on August 6, 1945 and August 9, 1945, respectively. These two events did not only lead to the end of World War II, but it also defined the place of the United States as a major power that entered into the international system in its own right.

From thence on, America began to play a leading role in the global political scene, including its pioneering role in the formation of the United Nations Organization in 1945. However, this niche which the United States has carved for itself in the international system became a threat to the empire ambition of the then Union of Soviet Socialist Republic (U.S.S.R.) that espoused the Breshnev Doctrine of Communist Internationalism. This led to the outbreak of the Cold War. To win the Cold War, the United States needed the support and mutual cooperation of countries in Western Europe who were the immediate potential victims of the threat of Soviet Communist expansionism.

This informed the cooperative relationship between the United States and Western Europe during the era of the Cold War. Hitherto, the United States has seen Western European countries as beneficial allies in the task of prosecuting the Monroe Doctrine of the containment of Communism and *ipso facto*, maintaining its super power status in the international arena. This was the rationale for United States membership of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO). With the cooperation and assistance of Western European Countries, the world witnessed the break up of the Soviet Union in 1989, the independence of the former Soviet Republics, some of which now become members of the European Union, and the "triumph of capitalism" as a global economic ideology with the United States as its main custodian.

Regrettably, after the break up of the Soviet empire and consequent end of the Cold War, the United States still sees Western European Countries, who have now merged to form a supra-national organization, the European Union, as a beneficial ally. It still pursues a cooperative relationship with the EU as well as mutually inclusive foreign and military policies. For example, the United States is still a member of NATO, even though the *casus foederis* no more subsists. The United States' continued support to and promotion of a closer cooperation with the European Union is based on its desire to compensate Western European countries for their long support during the Cold War and thereby ensure their continued support for her continued dominance of international politics.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The United States' belief that its continued support to and promotion of a closer cooperation with the European Union is in its interest is mistaken. The fact that the EU is not going to give the United States the same level of support and commitment as obtained during the Cold War is not lost to the U.S. itself. This is why it relies on Britain to represent its interest within the EU. This informs its support for the continued membership of Britain in the EU until the recent Brexit referendum where Britain voted to opt out of the EU.

Bromund, and Gardiner (2014:1) believes that U.S. pressure for Britain to remain in the EU with the hope that Britain would support its interest within the EU is short-sighted and fallacious. This, according to them, is because "after 1991, when the Cold War was conclusively over, the policy of European integration was no longer in the U.S. interest". The structure of bureaucratic centralism of the EU is against the avowed policy of "economic freedom and limited government" of the United States (Bromund, *et. al.*, 2014:2). The desire of the United States therefore to facilitate a more democratic

and economically free EU using Britain as an instrument has met with frustration. Bromund, *et. al.*, (2014:2) cite the failure of the British government to support the United States' expectation of blocking the appointment of Jean-Claude Juncker, a Euro federalist as the president of the European Commission as a mark of such frustration.

The problem therefore is that the European Union's integration policy is clearly against the interest of the United States. Such close collaboration between European nations was an asset during the Cold War because it fostered unity of purpose and ensured that the communist bloc could not break the solidarity engendered thereby. This kept communism in check. However, after the Cold War, the EU has consolidated its super-state structure, usurped the sovereignties of the member states and promoted the rule by bureaucrats.

LITERATURE REVIEW

THE EU'S GOAL OF WORLD GOVERNMENT AND THE FUTURE OF THE US AS THE MAJOR SUPERPOWER

The US has enjoyed a position of power among the world powers and has hitherto been erroneously seen as the locus of a prospective world government until the emergence of the EU because of its strong and wealthy economy as well as its military might. That prospect of global control is the major goal of the EU from its inception. The creation of a world government which will regulate the interaction among governments and assure the rights arising from social and economic globalization is at the center of EU's integration project. This has informed the supranational structure and the configuration of offices in the organs of the EU. An example is the plan to create a super-powerful EU president.

In his reaction to the discovery of the intention of European Union foreign ministers to create a super-powerful EU president by merging the offices of the president of the European Council and that of the president of the European Commission, Independent Labour peer Lord Stoddart of Swindon said, "This is a plot by people who want to abolish nation states and create a United States of Europe." His concern was for the sovereignty of Britain, and therefore, he called on Britain to "...leave the EU and become an independent nation" (LVB Research, 2012:1). The plan to merge the two offices for one bureaucrat to handle the two jobs is predicated on the bitter rivalry between Mr. Jose Manuel Barroso, the former president of the European Commission and Mr. Herman Van Rompuy, the former president of the European Council which has incapacitated the European Union from speaking with a single voice, especially in the face of the euro zone crisis (LVB Research, 2012:5).

Horsley (2002:3) mentions the French elder statesman, Valerie Giscard d'Estaing, the chairman of the 105-member Convention that merged and modified all the treaties of the European Union to form the European Union Constitution, which he christened the "Convention on the Future of Europe" as a major supporter of the replacement of the name, "European Union" with the "United States of Europe." The Insider corroborates this fact of creating a "United States of Europe." Describing the European Union's "... official Constitution for the "United States of Europe." This is facilitated by the granting of dual citizenship to citizens of

member countries by the European Union Constitution.
The Lisbon Treaty bestows the amendment of the Treaty of the European Union upon the European Parliament as against the pre-Lisbon arrangement where Article 48 of the Treaty of the European Union gave Member States the privilege to propose a revision of a treaty through the ordinary legislative procedure. This is a further diminution of the sovereignty of member states to facilitate EU's global agenda and this has profound implications for US global policy of democracy and limited government.

US-EU RELATIONSHIP

Given the strategic place of the United States in global politics and economy, some scholars have been interested in the relationship between the EU and the US. Emmott, and Palmer (2012:1) believe that the EU and the US account for about half the world's economic output and nearly a third of world trade. Unfortunately, the European debt crises, on the one hand, and America's elusive economic growth, on the other hand, are pushing both sides to consider removing barriers to trade between them. Where this happens, the EU will benefit more as European economic output will increase "... by 122 billion euros (\$158 billion) a year for Europe alone and add 0.52 percent to the EU's gross domestic product in the long term..." Emmott, *et. al.* (2012:2) declares that the trade links between the EU and the US are without equal. According to them, "transatlantic trade in goods and services is worth \$700 billion a year. Total U.S. annual investment in the European Union is higher than in all of Asia, while EU investment in the US far outstrips EU investment in India and China combined." The report concludes that a deal between the two – the EU and the US – would make imports and exports cheaper and easier for businessmen on both sides.

Businesses on both sides would like an agreement in which a car tested for safety in the US would not have to be tested again in Europe, and a drug deemed safe by Brussels would not have to be approved as well by the U.S. government. Small companies who make household appliances, lighting and wiring equipment say prohibitive costs of certifying products for different requirements in Europe and the US make it impossible currently to export, according to a public consultation by Brussels-based lobby group Business Europe (Emmott, *et. al.* 2012:2).

Despite the seeming cooperative relationship, European leaders have not been favorably disposed to countries that have intimate economic or political ties with the United States. This is the explanation for President Charles de Gaulle's two times veto of the United Kingdom's membership of the European Economic Community (EEC) in 1963 and 1967. This action was not because of Britain's pioneering role in the formation of the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) as some scholars presume, but because of her close ties with the United States of America. Moreover, underneath the seemingly cooperative relationship between the EU and the US, there has been a subtle element of competition, if not suspicion, especially from the European end of the relationship.

Jewish News (2019) made an allusion to an article published in 2002 that heralded the European Union as the emerging superpower and the main competitor to the United States on the world stage after the Cold War instead of China, Russia or the Islamic world was envisaged.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study adopted the theory of power as a more humane variant of realism. International politics is generally regarded as a game of power. Some scholars have described it as a game the stronger and more powerful members of the international system play. These scholars include Hans Morgenthau, Kenneth Waltz and Northedge. Among them, Hans Morgenthau seems to be the most vocal and consistent exponent of the power theory of international politics. In his *Politics Among Nations*, Morgenthau simply described international politics as "Power Politics" (1985:165). On his part, Kenneth Waltz described international politics as the realm of power, of struggle, and of accommodation in contra-distinction to national politics which, he described as the realm of authority, of administration, and of law (Waltz, 1979:113). To Northedge, International Politics (are) those mutual dealings of governments representing sovereign states which involve considerations of status, standing, power and prestige of the general welfare of peoples as an object of governmental action (Northedge, and Donelan 1971:19). Emphasis here is on the types of power a nation possesses, either political, economic or military power. In this study, economic power is regarded as most important determinant of the emerging status of the two political units under study.

METHODOLOGY

This work adopted a qualitative approach without assuming any statistical sophistication to analyze the power relationship between the US and the EU. Espousing John McCormick's view that the Cold War driven definition of superpower using military might is no longer germane to the determination of the superpower status (Dávila, 2002), this study limited its focus on the economic power of the US and the EU. The study examined the trade relations between the US and the EU using data provided by the United States Census Bureau and the U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis and also data provided by Eurostat. Through simple observation of the data provided by the above bodies, the study drew conclusions on the unfolding economic strength of the two political units under study.

The US Census Bureau and the U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis, through the Department of Commerce report of October 5, 2016 has shown that the US "...international trade deficit in goods and services increased to \$40.7 billion in August from \$39.5 billion in July (revised), as imports increased more than exports". This is illustrated in Figure 1

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Figure 1: U.S. International Trade in Goods and Services

Source: U.S. Census Bureau & U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis. Available at: https://www.census.gov/foreign-trade/Press-Release/current_press_release/ft900.pdf

Conversely, the European Union's share of world trade has been on the increase as shown in figure 2

Figure 2: International trade data for 2014

Source: Eurostat. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/images/7/7e/Main_players_for_international_trade%2C_2014_%28billion_EUR%29_YB16.png. Accessed on Oct 7, 2016

Figure 2 reveals that the US exports dropped drastically while its imports increased tremendously. On the other hand, the EU trade balance shows an increase in exports above its imports.

This trend has led to a negative balance of trade for the US. This is illustrated in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Trade balance for international trade, 2004 and 2014(billion EUR)

Source: Eurostat. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/images/c/ce/Trade_balance_for_international_trade%2C_2004_and_2014_%28billion_EUR%29_YB16.png

Figure 3 shows that the US had a whopping deficit balance of trade of above 400 billion Euros in 2004 as against a deficit balance of less than 100 billion Euros for the EU.

Eurostat statistics also reveal that EU exports so far exceeds its imports from the US. This definitely accounts for the positive balance of EU trade with the US. If this trend continues, EU economy is likely going to outgrow the US economy in the future thereby giving the EU an edge over the US economically. This is illustrated in figure 4.

Figure 4:
 Extra EU-28 trade by main trading partners, EU-28, 2005 and 2015 (billion
 EUR) YB16

Source: Eurostat: Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/images/c/cc/Extra_EU-28_trade_by_main_trading_partners%2C_EU-28%2C_2005_and_2015_%28%2B%29_%28billion_EUR%29_YB16.png

Figure 5: Shares in the world market for exports, 2014 (% share of world exports) YB16

Figure 6:

Shares in the world market for imports, 2014 (% share of world imports)YB16

Eurostat's pie chart of share of world exports and imports in Figures 5 and 6 above clearly illustrates the position of the US vis-à-vis the EU in world trade. Figure 5, on the one hand, shows that the EU controls 15 per cent of world exports while the US controls 12.2 per cent. On the other hand, figure 6 shows that the US imports more (15.9%) globally while the EU imports less (14.8%).

EU VERSUS USA: COOPERATION OR COMPETITION?

It has been the European Union's desire to compete favorably with the United States, right from the days of the European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC). This informed Jean Monnet's inspiration for the Schuman declaration which formed the foundation stone for the formation of the European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC). It was Jean Monnet's belief that "...if the nations of Europe were to resume a dominant role in world affairs, they had to speak with one voice and command resources comparable to those of the United States" (Microsoft Encarta, 2009). This led to his election as the president of the High Authority of the European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC).

In the present setting, the European judicial system is fashioned in total imitation of the American Supreme Court. Lord Judge foresees the creation of a "European judicial system" and the emergence of "... a court with the equivalent jurisdiction throughout Europe of that enjoyed by the Supreme Court in the United States of America?" (Soeren, 2014:2). He expressed his total aversion to the exportation of parliamentary supremacy by an external court and the possible effect of such anomaly in the long term.

Meanwhile, the leadership of the EU has been unequivocal about the formation of a world government, or at least, a supranational union that will ultimately compete

favorably with the US (Alexandar, 2011). Statements by some leaders of the Union prove that the whole aim of the EU is to merge and become economically and militarily stronger than the US and her allies.

As a European response to U.S. President Donald Trump's "America First" doctrine, the French President, Emmanuel Macron on January 28, 2019 is quoted as calling for a European renaissance with this words: "Europe must take control of its future by spending more on its own defense and technologies, tightening its borders, standing up to the world's superpowers on trade while also fighting climate change and protecting European jobs" (Burdeau, 2019:1). On trade, Macron "...said the EU should hire European companies for 'strategic industries and public procurement,' just as the United States and China do in their countries" (Burdeau, 2019:1).

Trump's doctrine of "America First" has led to a detachment of former allies and a growing skepticism in the US toward global engagement and this has further heightened the suspicion and competition of the EU against the US. This explains the skepticism of the European leaders to Joe Biden and Democrats' belief that they will restore the camaraderie between the US and the EU when democrats take over government in 2020 (Witte, and Birnbaum, 2019).

The structure and machinery of the European Union confirms the fact that the EU is in apparent competition with the US. Skousen (2011:3) shows that the incremental shift of power from the member nations to the EU as provided for in the European Constitution is to afford the European Union "... more power to confront the US jointly." The anti-American spirit is also noticeable in the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) where the drive of smaller nations is to vote in former "... Eastern bloc nations to counter the traditional Big 4 (US, Britain, France, and Germany)" (Skousen, 2011:3). If this attitude persists and if the EU's integration process continues to its logical conclusion as envisaged by its leadership, it may eventually bring the EU to a preponderant position vis-à-vis the US in the prospective New World Order.

The global impact a stronger European Union will have in the UN need not be overemphasized. If the global tax proposed by the UN comes into effect, most of the funding of the UN will come from the tax of EU member countries and the UN will cease to be dependent on the US for funding. On the other hand, where EU member countries unanimously withhold their contributions to the UN, the world body would be paralyzed and may probably collapse. With 28 members, the EU already has controlling votes in the UN. Moreover, there is an ongoing move for other states to join the EU (Koenig, 2012:1). Reding (2002) foresees the possibility of an eventual accession of the entire Europe, including Russia and Turkey. This, according to him, will not only boost the EU's economy but will increase its population to about 800 million which he considers almost equal to that of India or China. With this possible enlargement, the EU will undoubtedly control the UN in particular and the entire world in general.

This fact is not lost to the US, but surprisingly, it still backs, encourages and supports the integration process which has promoted economic stagnation and rule by bureaucrats and thus stands directly on the head of the policies of national sovereignty, economic freedom and limited government which America espouses.

On the contrary, EU leaders are desperately seeking for opportunity to dislodge US dominance, especially in the technology sector. Guttenberg is quoted by Michels (2019)

as attacking American tech companies like Facebook, Google and Amazon that their power is posing a threat to the free democratic world order.

The European Commission "... wants the widest deal possible, including access for EU companies to America, state-level government purchasing contracts and services" (Emmott, *et. al.* 2012:2). This will definitely lead to the integration of the two economies in the long run. This may culminate in political integration of the US and the EU thereby fast tracking the formation of the envisioned world government with the center at the stronger end of the merger. This would likely be Western Europe if the current trend persists.

This is also one of the major reasons for the EU's desire to establish a free trade area with the US. Little wonder therefore that although the European Union no more trusts the US as during the era of the Cold War, yet it started negotiations of a free-trade deal with the US from the spring of 2013. This trade relations between the EU and the US is believed has the prospect of mutually increasing their world's economic output and also stemming the effect of the global financial crisis (GFC) in Europe (Emmott, *et. al.*, 2012).

Trade relations with the US may be one of the ways the EU hopes to obviate the effect of the debt crisis in Europe. The global financial crisis (GFC) had a battering effect on countries that joined the European Monetary System (EMS) since they are not permitted to adjust their monetary policies to cope with the global financial crisis. The EU therefore hopes to use the free trade relations with the US to bolster its economy to give the Union the economic advantage over the US itself. This has justified Britain's decision to remain outside the EMS. By eschewing the EMS, Britain before Brexit, had the liberty to adjust its monetary policy to cope with the global financial crisis, while countries like the Irish Republic that joined the EMS had not such liberty to adjust its monetary policy to cope with the global financial crisis (GFC). With Brexit therefore, Britain stands at an advantage in this regard in spite of the challenges which come with Brexit. This is the time for the US to assist Britain more to stand without the EU.

Since the rationale for the US continued support of Britain's membership of the EU was the fear that if Britain opts out of the European Union, it will affect its economy, the US should seek for other ways of collaboration with Britain. Bromund, *et. al.* (2014:1) have recommended that the other avenue for the US to assist Britain is the negotiation of a free trade area (FTA) between the US and Britain. According to them:

... the barrier that is blocking a U.S.-U.K. free trade area is the European Union. Since the early post-war years, the U.S. has supported European integration and the EU's efforts to subordinate democratic and sovereign nations to supranational control. This policy is a mistake. It is not an approach that the U.S., as a democracy, would accept for itself, and the U.S. should therefore not urge other democracies to go down a path that leads to the loss of national independence. The ultimate goal of the U.S.-U.K. free trade area, therefore, is to serve as both a symbol of and a real contribution to a shared Anglo-American rejection of supranational control and shared belief that government

must be based on national sovereignty and freedom.
(Bromund, *et. al.* 2014:1).

Until Brexit, the United Kingdom's membership of the EU was the major stumbling block to its negotiation of a Free Trade Area (FTA) with the US. Now that it has voted to leave the EU, the negotiation of a Free Trade Area (FTA) with the USA should be a priority and a possibility. Britain's commitment to the EU not only imposed juridical bounds against its entering into a free trade agreement with the US but also deterred the US from negotiating such agreement with her because any attempt by the US to "... negotiate a free trade area with the U.K. would be tantamount to approving of Britain's exit from the union" (Bromund, *et. al.*, 2014:2) and this, the US assumes would be a betrayal on its part of Europe's support to her during the Cold War. We can therefore agree with Bromund, *et. al.* 2014:1) that:

... the barrier that is blocking a U.S.–U.K. free trade area is the European Union.... The ultimate goal of the U.S.–U.K. free trade area, therefore, is to serve as both a symbol of and a real contribution to a shared Anglo–American rejection of supranational control and shared belief that government must be based on national sovereignty and freedom.

But surprisingly, successive administrations in the US have been opposed to Britain leaving the EU because of the fear of being misinterpreted as approving of Brexit." Moreover, the US has hitherto relied on the UK to back up its interests in the EU as the US is suspicious of the EU of not supporting its interest and vice versa. However, Bromund, *et. al.* (2014:3) believe that it is quite preposterous for the US to rely on the UK to defend its interest owing to her failure to block the selection of Jean-Claude Juncker, the Euro-federalist, as the president of the European Commission.

In spite of this, the US continued to support British membership of the EU even with the regimented "... top-down regulation and supranational..." bureaucratic structure of the EU which is against the "...economic freedom and limited government policy which the US espouses (Bromund, *et. al.*, 2014:3). The explanation for this, according to Bromund, *et. al.* (2014:4), is that the United States of America either feels obligated to continue to support these European democracies whose support was so pivotal to winning the Cold War or it is mistaken to believe that the EU is a European Free Trade Area (EFTA) which the United Kingdom originally intended it to be but was opposed by France. With France's influence, the EU instead took on a supranational character usurping the "...independent trading policies of its member nations"(Bromund, *et. al.* 2014:4).

In the defense sector, World Affairs Brief(2011:4) believe that the influence of the US in the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) is on the decline. According to the report, "Europe doesn't trust the US anymore to be an honest partner. They all know the US wants to run the whole show." EU member countries, therefore, forge a common front to fight against the US. World Affairs Brief (2011:4) reports that one of the proposals in the EU constitution is increased power to jointly confront the US.

This distrust may be due to the US continued expansion of its military capability and bases all over the world after the end of the Cold War. Engdahl (2012:1) reports that:

Since the collapse of the Soviet Union and the nominal end of the Cold War some twenty years back, rather than reducing the size of its mammoth defense spending, the US Congress and all US Presidents have enormously expanded spending for new weapons systems, increased permanent military bases around the world and expansion of NATO not only to former Warsaw Pact countries on Russia's immediate periphery; it also has expanded NATO and US military presence deep into Asia on the perimeters of China through its conduct of the Afghan war and related campaigns.

Leaders of the EU viewed President Barack Obama's statement during his visit to Australia in 2011 with suspicion and as proof of the continued US global agenda:

With most of the world's nuclear power and some half of humanity, Asia will largely define whether the century ahead will be marked by conflict or cooperation...As President, I have, therefore, made a deliberate and strategic decision — as a Pacific nation, the United States will play a larger and long-term role in shaping this region and its future...I have directed my national security team to make our presence and mission in the Asia Pacific a top priority...As we plan and budget for the future, we will allocate the resources necessary to maintain our strong military presence in this region. We will preserve our unique ability to project power and deter threats to peace...Our enduring interests in the region demand our enduring presence in the region. The United States is a Pacific power, and we are here to stay. Indeed, we are already modernizing America's defense posture across the Asia Pacific. It will be more broadly distributed — maintaining our strong presence in Japan and the Korean Peninsula, while enhancing our presence in Southeast Asia. Our posture will be more flexible — with new capabilities to ensure that our forces can operate freely ... I believe we can address shared challenges, such as proliferation and maritime security, including cooperation in the South China Sea (Engdahl, 2012:2)

This accounts for the EU's impression about the US as an impostor not as a collaborator. To stem the US continued dominance therefore, leaders of the EU are vitally

interested in what goes on in that country. In July 2012, the United Kingdom's Secretary of State for Defense, Phillip Hammond, drew the attention of EU's NATO members to the above defense policy of the US towards the Asia-Pacific insinuating that it was targeted towards China as an emerging global power (Engdahl, 2012:2). While this study does not diminish the rise of China as an emerging global superpower, it is rather concerned with the continued support of the US gives to the global agenda of its potential rival, the EU.

CONCLUSION

The US support for European integration is not based on the hope that it would promote prosperity and democracy, but it is an indication of the ancient understanding and cooperation of the West to unite together for the control of the rest of the world. The United States is ever ready to support and encourage the European Union to acquire more nations as members to build up its power potential believing that such power would never threaten its existence but it would prepare the European Union for a possible alliance for the control of the world in the near future.

But contrary to the realist prediction of the decline and final demise of Europe's global influence, Moravcsik (2009) believes that Europe's global influence is actually on the rise. He writes:

The conventional wisdom has it that the global influence of Europe is in decline. This essay argues, to the contrary, that Europe remains the only other global superpower besides the United States. It is the world's second military power and pre-eminent civilian power. Its power is, in fact, rising. For the foreseeable future it is likely to remain one of two superpowers in a bipolar world (Moravcsik, 2009).

This affirms the thesis of this study that based on its size and the global trend of its trade relations as well its increasing global political influence, the EU will soon achieve a superpower status which will enable it to favorably compete with, if not, overwhelm the US in the near future. Western Europe's integration can therefore be seen as a conspiracy against the United States' preeminence in the international system. Member nations willingly acquiesce to the increment in the power of the EU and the consequent reduction in their sovereign status in order to build a formidable team against the US (Griffiths, 2011).

In spite of the EU's lethargic economic progress, bureaucratic centralism, demographic divisiveness, and military weakness, it is daily consolidating a global match or even surpass the strength of the US and other regional international organizations. It will therefore become a world force that would possible be able to police the entire globe in the near future. This is the avowed goal of the leadership of the EU. But this goal has serious implications for the super power status of the United States of America.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study recommends that:

1. The United States should realize that cooperation and support for European integration as compensation to Western Europe's support during the Cold War is against its own global interest.
2. The future of the United States preeminence in the international system lies in its realization that with the end of the Cold War, the epoch's understanding and cooperation with Western Europe has given way to a new spirit of competition for dominance by the EU.
3. In this era of balance of terror where more nations have acquired nuclear capability vis-à-vis the situation in 1945, the effectiveness of military might as an instrument of policy has drastically reduced. The assurance of the US super power status lies in its ability to address the current imbalance in trade that exists between it and the EU.

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